

Relationship between Principals' Managerial Competencies and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

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Abstract

This study ascertained the relationship between principals' managerial competencies and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Five research questions guided the study while five hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational research design was employed for the study. The population of the study comprised 6145 secondary school teachers in the 267 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample for the study comprised 600 secondary school teachers drawn from the population of the study using simple random sampling technique. The instruments for data collection were two sets of questionnaire titled: 'Questionnaire on Principals' Managerial Competencies (QUPMAC)' and Teacher's Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ). The questionnaires were validated by three experts in Faculty of Education in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The questionnaires were trial-tested using 20 secondary school teachers in public secondary schools in Enugu State which was subjected to internal consistency reliability technique using Cronbach Alpha statistics. These yielded a mean reliability coefficient of 0.78 for QUPMAC, and 0.80 for TJPQ. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used in answering the research questions while regression statistical analysis was used for testing the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that technical interpersonal, conceptual, monitoring and planning competencies have positive relationship with teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study further revealed that principals' planning competence and principals' interpersonal competence have the highest positive relationship with teachers' job performance. The study further revealed that there is a significant relationship between principals' managerial competencies in all its' indicators and teachers' job performance. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that school administrators should regularly participate in leadership development programmes that focus on essential managerial competencies such as interpersonal managerial competence, planning managerial competence, technical managerial competence, conceptual managerial competence and monitoring managerial competence. This will get them equipped to ensure effective teachers' job performance in secondary schools.

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Introduction

Education in Nigeria, as in many other nations, is structured into pre-primary, primary, secondary, and tertiary levels. The Nigerian government sees education as a powerful tool for national development, and policy implementation across levels reflects this. Secondary education, a critical link between primary and tertiary stages, equips students with foundational knowledge for advanced studies and prepares them for societal roles. It is categorized into public and private schools. The goals of secondary education in Nigeria include offering further learning opportunities irrespective of background, preparing students for employment through vocational and technical training, and fostering individual development (FRN, 2013). These goals, however, hinge significantly on the contributions of teachers as curriculum implementers (Enose, 2018).

Teaching is a respected and demanding profession requiring mastery, dedication, and effectiveness. Okoye (2018) noted that only professionally qualified teachers can effectively meet teaching demands. Teachers are seen as nation builders, moral models, and pillars of educational systems (Panda, 2017). Their job performance reflects in teaching effectiveness, classroom management, and contribution to students' academic growth. Fred and Allan (2018) emphasized that teachers' job performance includes their commitment to pedagogy, moral standards, and academic excellence. According to Baskan and Ayda (2018), effective job performance also involves organized lesson delivery, classroom control, and motivation of students. However, signs of inadequate job performance among teachers in some public secondary schools in Anambra State are evident. As a teacher within the study area, the researcher observed absenteeism, poor commitment, ineffective classroom management, and neglect of instructional duties. These signs prompted a deeper inquiry into possible underlying causes. Salmah and Andi (2020) posited that teachers' job performance is influenced by factors like the school environment and principal leadership.

In this context, the role of the school principal becomes critical. Principals serve as the chief administrators of secondary schools, charged with managing resources and ensuring effective teaching and learning. They influence staff performance, school climate, and instructional delivery (Djibo & Al-Taneiji, 2018). A principal's effectiveness largely depends on managerial competencies—the ability to plan, coordinate, supervise, and lead the school toward its goals (Nnebedum & Akinfolarin, 2017). These competencies include technical, interpersonal, conceptual, monitoring, and planning skills (Sidek & Mohamad, 2014; Odu-Dikoro, 2022).

Technical competence entails specialized knowledge of school operations and instructional processes (Ayalew et al., 2022). Interpersonal competence relates to collaboration, communication, and motivation skills necessary for fostering team spirit (Victor, 2017). Conceptual competence enables principals to view the school system holistically, understanding how various departments interact (Batra & Sharma, 2017). Monitoring competence ensures the principal evaluates instructional delivery and teacher performance, providing feedback and enforcing accountability (Fullan, 2015). Planning competence equips principals with foresight, allowing them to align resources with goals and respond to challenges effectively (Giami & Obiechina, 2019).

Research findings on the correlation between principals' managerial competencies and teachers' job performance are mixed. While Akinfolarin (2017), Ezeugbor & Akinfolarin (2018), and Obi et al. (2022) observed a gap in principals' competencies, others like Salmah and Andi (2020), Murniati and Wahidy (2021), and Owan and Agunwa (2022) found positive relationships between principal competence and teacher effectiveness. These contrasting views and the researcher's firsthand observations underscore the need to explore the relationship between principals' managerial competencies and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Specifically, the study sought to ascertain:

1. the relationship between principals' technical competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. the relationship between principals' interpersonal competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. the relationship between principals' conceptual competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
4. the relationship between principals' monitoring competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
5. the relationship between principals' planning competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. what is the relationship between principals' technical competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. what is the relationship between principals' interpersonal competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. what is the relationship between principals' conceptual competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
4. what is the relationship between principals' monitoring competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
5. what is the relationship between principals' planning competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. there is no significant relationship between principals' technical competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. there is no significant relationship between principals' interpersonal competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. there is no significant relationship between principals' conceptual competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

4. there is no significant relationship between principals' monitoring competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
5. there is no significant relationship between principals' planning competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

Behavioural Theory of Leadership (Blake and Mouton, 1964)

The most well-known behavioural theory of leadership was created by Robert Blake and Jane Mouton (1964). The theory is otherwise referred to as the Managerial Grid. The behavioural theory of leadership is focused on identifying the overt actions of effective leaders that distinguish them from ineffective leaders. It is believed that by creating taxonomy of behaviours linked to effective leadership, as the reasoning goes, then others can learn how to also be leaders. All they have to do is to act in the same way as effective leaders. By analysing an effective leader along these two dimensions, Robert Blake and Jane Mouton developed the Managerial Grid of an effective leadership which includes: accommodating style, indifferent style, sound style, dictatorial style and status quo style. The earlier version of behavioural theory of leadership presented leaders in the light of the concepts of 'consideration' and 'initiating structure'. The 'consideration' factor was primarily about relationships, implying that leaders that displayed this priority were supportive of employees, communicated well and were concerned about their employees' feelings. On the other hand 'initiating structure' was primarily about accomplishing tasks, implying that leaders that displayed these competencies were concerned with scheduling work, planning and coordinating work-related tasks while maintaining specific standards.

In the light of the foregoing, the behavioural theory of leadership posits that effective leaders engage in specific types of behaviour (which other can observe and learn) which results in improved team performance. This implies that when effective leaders are in-charge, they exhibit certain competencies that are worthy of effective leaders, the members of their team looks at those competencies, imbibes them and in-turn become effective leaders in their own leadership roles, thereby yielding positive team performance.

This theory is of essence to this study in the sense that the realization of the goals of secondary education requires maximum job performance. The behavioural theory posits that effective leaders engage in specific types of behaviour which result in improved team performance. This is because, being mindful of the supposed competencies of an effective leader can go a long way in helping to train people to become effective leaders themselves, thus improving overall performance. As such, the principal as the head is at the pinnacle of influence not just to the teachers but also to other staff members of the school. As a consequence of that, the competencies a principal possesses have a resultant effect on the overall performance of his teachers. This goes to say that in this journey of realization of the goals of secondary education, aside other intervening factors, the characteristics of the individuals at the helm of affairs matters a lot. If the teachers are placed under a principal that posses requisite managerial competencies,

there are chances that the teachers will emulate those competencies and exemplify them in their job performance. However, if the reverse is the case, it may negatively impact the teachers' performance. This study is related to this theory because it emphasises the importance of a principal's managerial competencies, and thus suggesting that effective management makes a major difference in how well a school performs.

Method

The present study adopted correlational research design. The population of the study comprised 6,145 secondary school teachers in the 267 public secondary schools across the six education zones in Anambra State. The sample for the study comprised 600 secondary school teachers drawn from the population using multi-stage random sampling technique. Out of the six education zones, three zones—Awka, Ogidi, and Onitsha—were selected using simple random sampling. From each selected zone, 10 public secondary schools were randomly selected, making a total of 30 schools. From each of these schools, 20 secondary school teachers were randomly chosen, resulting in a total sample of 600 teachers used for the study. The instruments for data collection were two structured questionnaires titled: “Questionnaire on Principals’ Managerial Competencies (QUPMAC)” and “Teachers’ Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)”. QUPMAC had two sections, A and B. Section A contained the bio-data of the respondents, while Section B contained 31 items designed to elicit responses from the teachers on their principals’ managerial competencies. TJPQ on the other hand had 16 items designed to assess the job performance of teachers. Both QUPMAC and TJPQ were structured on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The scores for positive statements were weighted 4, 3, 2, and 1 for SA to SD respectively, while the negative statements were weighted 1, 2, 3, and 4 for SA to SD respectively. The instruments were subjected to face validation by three experts: two from the Department of Educational Management and Policy, and one from the Department of Educational Foundations (Measurement and Evaluation), all from the Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The questionnaires were also trial-tested using 20 secondary school teachers from public secondary schools in Enugu State, and their responses were analyzed for internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha reliability statistics. This yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.78 for QUPMAC and 0.80 for TJPQ, indicating that the instruments were reliable. A total of 592 questionnaires were successfully retrieved out of the 600 distributed, yielding a 98.67% return rate, and were used for data analysis. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions, while regression statistical analysis was employed to test the hypotheses.

Results

Research Question One: What is the Relationship between Principals’ Technical Competence And Teachers’ Job Performance In Public Secondary Schools In Anambra State?

Table 1: Pearson r on the Relationship between Principals’ Technical Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

S/N	Source of Variation	N	R	Remark
1	Principals’ Technical Competence	592	0.72	High Positive Relationship
2	Teachers’ Job Performance			

Data presented in Table 1 reveals a Pearson product moment correlation co-efficient computed to determine the relationship between principals’ technical competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Relationship index of 0.72 as revealed in the regression coefficient rule is an indication of high positive relationship. The result as seen in the table thus reveals that there is a high positive relationship between principals’ technical competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools.

Research Question Two: What is the Relationship between Principals’ Interpersonal Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Pearson r on the Relationship between Principals’ Interpersonal Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

S/N	Source of Variation	N	R	Remark
1	Principals’ Interpersonal Competence	592	0.90	Very High Positive Relationship
2	Teachers’ Job Performance			

Data presented in Table 2 reveals a Pearson product moment correlation co-efficient computed to determine the relationship between principals’ interpersonal competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Relationship index of 0.90 as revealed in the regression coefficient rule is an indication of very high positive relationship. The result as seen in the table thus reveals that there is a very high positive relationship between principals’ interpersonal competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question Three: What is the Relationship between Principals’ Conceptual Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: Pearson r on the Relationship between Principals’ Conceptual Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

S/N	Source of Variation	N	R	Remark
1.	Principals’ Conceptual Competence	592	0.67	High Positive Relationship
2.	Teachers’ Job Performance			

Data presented in Table 3 reveals a Pearson product moment correlation co-efficient computed to determine the correlation between principals’ conceptual competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra state. Relationship index of 0.67 as revealed in the regression coefficient rule is an indication of high positive correlation. The result as seen in the table thus reveals that there is a high positive relationship between principals’ conceptual competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question Four: What is the Relationship between Principals’ Monitoring Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

Table 4: Pearson r on the Relationship between Principals’ Monitoring Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

S/N	Source of Variation	N	R	Remark
1	Principals’ Monitoring Competence	592	0.69	High Positive Relationship
2	Teachers’ Job Performance			

Data presented in Table 4 reveals a Pearson product moment correlation co-efficient computed to determine the relationship between principals’ monitoring competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Relationship index of 0.69 as revealed in the regression coefficient rule is an indication of high positive relationship. The result as seen in the table thus reveals that there is a high positive relationship between principals’ monitoring competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question Five: What is the Relationship between Principals’ Planning Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

Table 5: Pearson r on the Relationship between Principals’ Planning Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

S/N	Source of Variation	N	R	Remark
1	Principals’ Planning Competence	592	0.85	Very High Positive Relationship
2	Teachers’ Job Performance			

Data presented in Table 5 reveals a Pearson product moment correlation co-efficient computed to determine the relationship between principals’ planning competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Correlation index of 0.85 as revealed in the regression coefficient rule is an indication of high positive relationship. The result as seen in the table thus reveals that there is a very high positive relationship between principals’ planning competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools.

Hypothesis One: There is no Significant Relationship between Principals’ Technical Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Test of Significance of Pearson Relationship between Principals’ Technical Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

S/N	Source of Variation	N	R	p-value	Remark
1	Principals’ Technical Competence	592	0.49	0.00	Significant
2	Teachers’ Job Performance				

Table 6 shows that there is a significant relationship between principals’ technical competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The calculated r (0.49) had $P.values < 0.05$. The 1st null hypothesis was therefore not accepted.

Hypothesis Two: There is no Significant Relationship between Principals’ Interpersonal Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Table 7: Pearson r on the Relationship between Principals’ Interpersonal Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Gender	Source of Variation	N	R	p-value	Remark
1	Principals’ Interpersonal Competence	592	0.57	.02	Significant
2	Teachers’ Job Performance				

Table 7 shows that there is a significant correlation existing between principals' interpersonal competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The calculated r (0.57) had P .values<0.05. The 2nd null hypothesis was therefore not accepted.

Hypothesis Three: There is no Significant Relationship between Principals' Conceptual Competence and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Table 8: Pearson r on the Relationship between Principals' Conceptual Competence and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

S/N	Source of Variation	N	R	p-value	Remark
1	Principals' Conceptual Competence	592	0.51	0.00	Significant
2	Teachers' Job Performance				

As shown in Table 8, there is a significant relationship between principals' conceptual competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The calculated r (0.51) had P .values <0.05. The 3rd null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis Four: There is no Significant Relationship between Principals' Monitoring Competence and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Table 9: Test of Significance of Pearson Relationship between Principals' Monitoring Competence and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

S/N	Source of Variation	N	R	p-value	Remark
1.	Principals' Monitoring Competence	592	0.58	0.00	Significant
2.	Teachers' Job Performance				

Table 9 shows that there is a significant relationship between principals' monitoring competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The calculated r (0.58) had P .values <0.05. The 4th null hypothesis was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis Five: There is no Significant Relationship between Principals’ Planning Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Table 10: Pearson r on the Relationship between Principals’ Planning Competence and Teachers’ Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

S/N	Source of Variation	N	R	p-value	Remark
1.	Principals’ Planning Competence	592	0.52	.00	Significant
2.	Teachers’ Job Performance				

Table 10 shows that there is a significant relationship between principals’ planning competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The calculated r (0.52) had *P*.values <0.05. The 5th null hypothesis was not accepted.

Discussion

As seen in Tables 1 and 6, the findings of the study revealed that there is a high positive relationship between principals’ technical competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The test of significance of Pearson correlation revealed that there is a significant relationship between principals’ technical competence and teachers’ job performance, a consequence of which the null hypothesis was rejected. The findings of the study agree with Yulia-Rachmawati and Santosa (2020) who revealed that principals’ managerial competence is a significant factor in enhancing school establishment and creativity, and that technical competence manifests in responsive management, productive school culture, and human resource development. The findings also align with May, Abdurrahman and Sowiyah (2020) who found that principal managerial competence positively and significantly influenced teacher performance in public vocational high schools.

As seen in Tables 2 and 7, the findings of the study revealed that there is a very high positive relationship between principals’ interpersonal competence and teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The test of significance of Pearson correlation revealed a significant relationship between interpersonal competence and teachers’ job performance, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The findings are in agreement with Salmah and Andi (2020) who found a significant influence of principals’ interpersonal competence on teachers’ performance in junior high schools. This implies that the higher the interpersonal competence of the principal, the higher the teachers’ job performance. The findings also align with Yulia-Rachmawati and Santosa (2020) who found that interpersonal competence is characterized by respectful and collaborative leadership. Similarly, the findings

agree with Muhaiyar (2018) who reported that improvement in teachers' performance is supported by democratic leadership, persuasive strategies, and cooperation between principals and teachers. Furthermore, Odu-dukoro (2022) found that interpersonal competence significantly influences teachers' job effectiveness in both public and private schools. The findings also resonate with Karisa (2015) who emphasized that team building, planning, coordination, and organizational competencies contribute significantly to teachers' productivity.

As seen in Tables 3 and 8, the findings of the study revealed that there is a high positive relationship between principals' conceptual competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The test of significance of Pearson correlation revealed a significant relationship, which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Although the findings contrast with Ayalew, Itegi, and Muchanje (2022) who found no significant relationship between conceptual competence and teachers' instructional effectiveness, they support Yulia-Rachmawati and Santosa (2020) who emphasized the importance of conceptual competence in strategic visioning and innovation. The findings also agree with Akinfolarin (2017) who noted that effective conceptual competence is shown in resource planning, financial accountability, and strategic school management. Furthermore, the findings align with Ganaden (2020) who described conceptual competence as essential for strategic thinking, innovation, and leadership development.

As seen in Tables 4 and 9, the study revealed a high positive relationship between principals' monitoring competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The test of significance of Pearson correlation showed a significant relationship between monitoring competence and teachers' job performance, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis. These findings agree with Obi, Ogbunude, and Chukwudolue (2022) who found that principals' communication and supervisory competencies significantly influence teachers' task performance. The findings are further supported by Owan and Agunwa (2022) who noted that principals' monitoring competence, manifested through supervision, leadership, and communication, is positively related to teachers' effectiveness in instructional delivery, record keeping, and class attendance.

As seen in Tables 5 and 10, the findings of the study revealed a very high positive relationship between principals' planning competence and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools. The test of significance of Pearson correlation revealed a significant relationship, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis. The findings are consistent with Amuche and Saleh (2013) who found that lack of professional competence in planning affects school management. They also support Ezeugbor and Akinfolarin (2018) who emphasized that poor managerial competencies, including planning, hinder effective student motivation and counseling. Moreover, the findings align with Murniati and Wahidy (2021) who found that principal managerial competence, school culture, and organizational culture significantly influence teachers' performance.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of data, it was concluded that principals' managerial competencies as it concerns its components as used in the study have a positive relationship with teachers' job

performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. These include: principals' technical competence, principals' interpersonal competence, principals' conceptual competence, principals' monitoring competence and principals' planning competence. Of all these principals' managerial competencies; principals' planning competence and principals' interpersonal competence have the highest positive relationship with teachers' job performance. Hypothesis testing revealed that a significant relationship exists between principals' managerial competencies in all its' indicators (including principals' technical competence, principals' interpersonal competence, principals' conceptual competence, principals' monitoring competence and principals' planning competence) and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. School administrators should regularly participate in leadership development programs that focus on essential managerial competencies such as interpersonal managerial competence, planning managerial competence, technical managerial competence, conceptual managerial competence and monitoring managerial competence. This will get them more equipped to ensure effective teachers' job performance in secondary schools.
2. Principals should create structures that allow teachers to participate in key decision-making processes. This could involve setting up committees or councils where teachers have a voice in school policies, curriculum design, and resource allocation. Such a step will go a long way to enhance their productivity.
3. Teachers should actively participate in school decision-making processes. By being involved in planning and school activities, teachers will feel more ownership over their work and more invested in the overall success of the school.
4. Teachers should strive to maintain open communication channels with their principals. Regularly engaging in dialogues about school needs, challenges, and personal development goals can lead to stronger relationships and a more conducive working environment.
5. Teachers should provide constructive feedback to school administrators about the challenges they face in the classroom and offer suggestions for improvements. This can help principals refine their management approach and better meet teachers' needs.

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